

OPPOSITION STRATEGIES IN HYBRID REGIMES: A COMPARATIVE PERSPECTIVE OF HUNGARY AND SERBIA

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The erosion of democratic governance has profoundly affected Central and Eastern Europe, with several countries undergoing a sustained wave of autocratization. This paper examines the constraints imposed by the regimes in Hungary and Serbia and the opposition strategies employed within these contexts, focusing on protests, boycotts, electoral tactics, and coalition-building, as well as their variation across electoral cycles since 2014. Building on a structured comparative framework, the study uses a theory-informed analytical matrix to evaluate the extent to which opposition actors confront regime-imposed obstacles and whether they generate comparable strategic responses. The findings indicate that an inconsistent strategic approach has been a defining feature of opposition behaviour over the past decade, likely contributing to weak performance. These patterns are observable in both countries and appear largely independent of institutional design, international positioning, or ideological specificities, suggesting that hybrid regimes tend to constrain opposition actors in ways that produce similar outcomes.

Key words: hybrid regimes; opposition strategies; elections; Hungary; Serbia.

1 INTRODUCTION: A TALE OF TWO REGIMES

For several years, reports from various international organizations have observed trends of democratic decline in the region of Central and Eastern Europe, with Serbia and Hungary often highlighted as drivers of autocratization. The Democracy Report (V-Dem 2024) distinguishes these two countries as rare European examples of electoral autocracies – alongside only Ukraine, Russia, Belarus, and Turkey. Moreover, Hungary is the only EU member state within the group, while Serbia stands out in this category as the only candidate country that

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has opened accession negotiation chapters with the EU, almost two-thirds of them. Nations in Transit report (Freedom House 2024) also categorizes both as hybrid regimes.

Hybrid regime represents a type of governance in which a democratic facade is maintained while power is concentrated, and elections are manipulated to secure electoral victories (Levitsky and Ziblatt 2018). These regimes combine the formal rules of democracy and the rule of law with manipulative authoritarian practices, in a manner that renders power transfer unlikely. This happens due to the uneven playing field: although elections appear to be competitive and even partly free, they are typically not fair, as ruling parties have almost unlimited access to institutions, financial and public resources, and the media, compared to their competitors who are faced with many practical obstacles (Levitsky and Way 2010).

Despite their differing ideological backgrounds, genesis of their respective parties, institutional distinctiveness, and disparate international contexts, the regimes of Aleksandar Vučić in Serbia and Viktor Orbán in Hungary exhibit significant similarities in the manner they maintain power. The inception of both regimes is viewed as an authoritarian response to the political and economic crises of the 2000s, especially the challenges faced by the political elites of newly democratized countries (Losoncz 2022). In Hungary, these issues culminated following EU accession, with poor performance of successive governments leading to a legitimacy crisis after 2006, compounded by the effects of the global financial crisis (Ágh 2013). In Serbia, the prolonged and delayed transition culminated in catastrophic effects from the economic crisis, which in 2011 caused unemployment to affect more than a quarter of the workforce (Jović and Bursać 2025). In both cases, disillusioned voters sought new options.

Since its first electoral victory in 2012, the Serbian Progressive Party (in Serbian *Srpska napredna stranka, SNS*) has begun to take over horizontal and vertical levels of power in Serbia, a process that was completed in 2017 when its leader Vučić transitioned from the position of PM to the one of a directly elected president. This consolidation of power fully centralized authority in a single individual in a political position that officially holds limited constitutional powers but draws unprecedented political strength from a commanding role within the ruling party (see Bursać and Vučićević 2021). It is precisely during this period that various international indices, NGOs, and political theorists begin to observe declining democracy in Serbia and categorize it as a hybrid regime. On the other hand, Viktor Orbán and his party Fidesz returned to power in the 2010 elections – after serving as PM in his earlier, significantly more liberal iteration from 1998 to 2002. As executive power in Hungary is more firmly institutionalized within the government, he didn't have an incentive to switch positions, like Vučić did. Orbán soon embarked on a transformation towards what he publicly calls "illiberal democracy", through a series of constitutional reforms, as well as through informal arrangements typical of hybrid regimes. Democratic institutions in Hungary are hollowed out by reducing elected positions (e.g., smaller parliaments, fewer local seats) and increasing the control of appointed power players over elected bodies. In both cases, authority is centralized in leaders who occupy the dual role of political competitors and arbiters, while charismatic leader-follower linkages legitimize autocratic governance under popular claims, leading Benedek (2025) to classify both regimes as paradigmatic examples of populist electoral autocracies.

Although Orbán's regime appears to be ideologically motivated by conservative right-wing ideas, while Vučić seems more a political opportunist who has shifted

from previously hardline nationalist standpoint towards political centre (Losoncz 2022), allowing for big-tent populist policies; the two leaders have formed a sort of informal political alliance (Ilić 2024). This is reflected in mutual support (both verbal and electoral – considering the significant Hungarian minority in Serbia that is awarded dual voting rights), as well as in joint projects, and finally lobbying efforts that Serbian regime receives in the European Union due to Orbán's favour. As Dukalskis (2021) argues, the survival of autocratic regimes is often aided by having a reliably autocratic neighbourhood, which provides a rationale for cooperation. Bozóki and Hegedűs (2018) observed a similar relationship between Orbán's government and the former PiS government in Poland, with both regimes mutually shielding one another from potential EU sanctions.

In addition to internal operational dynamics, the external environment also has a significant impact. Both regimes seem embedded in the Western-based international system. While Hungary is a member of the EU and NATO, which allows Orbán to dissent from within, Vučić's inherited position is much more complex. Troubled recent history, external constraints, partial reliance on Russia (providing energy supply and challenging Kosovo's independence), as well as the presence of Western power players in the Western Balkans, foster a kind of balancing act. Vučić is cooperative and is often perceived as a strategic partner of Washington, Brussels, Berlin, and other centres of power (Karnitschnig and Hajdari 2024). On the other hand, this enables him to make internal concessions regarding democracy and the rule of law to advance his regime. Whereas Orbán operates within a system that lacks effective mechanisms for disciplining its own members (Bozóki and Hegedűs 2018), Vučić, as the leader of a perpetual EU candidate, relies on the principle of stabilitocracy (see Bieber 2018), a trade-off in which he provides the desired geopolitical results in the Western Balkans in exchange for West's leniency regarding democratic values. If it maintains a minimal democratic facade, the Serbian regime appears able to undermine the electoral process, restrict media freedom, and erode the rule of law, provided it continues to demonstrate commitment to foreign policy objectives such as normalizing regional relations and gradually distancing Serbia and the Western Balkans from Russian influence. This relationship also allows the Serbian regime to domestically advance its position through appropriating the EU agenda while simultaneously pushing nationalist or pro-Russian narratives, effectively constraining the opposition's available space for political positioning (Laštro and Bieber 2021).

In any case, the effect of both regimes at the polls is the same: their replacement seems unlikely. Electoral victories are typically decisive, their ratings are high and largely based on the leader's popularity, while the opposition is usually fragmented and often appears powerless to oppose the ruling parties. Hence the SNS has not lost any presidential, parliamentary, provincial, or even local elections in Serbia since 2012; while Fidesz has generally won decisively in all parliamentary, European, and local elections, apart from the local elections in 2019, when the opposition managed to win in several major cities, including the capital Budapest. However, this did not significantly threaten the regime, which has since won parliamentary elections in 2022, European elections in 2024, and regained control of several cities in another local vote in 2024.

During this period, both Hungary and Serbia remain hybrid regimes rather than fully closed autocracies. As such, the potential for electoral turnover continues to hold significance for opposition actors, yet they consistently fail to achieve it. Our research seeks to understand why this is the case, and whether structural similarities of these regimes contribute to such patterns of opposition behaviour

and, consequently, to the repeated electoral outcomes. The outline of the study is as follows: this section will be followed with a theoretical one, analysing the existing explanation of political logic in hybrid regimes, but also proposing a methodological and hypothetical framework, continuing to a comparative analysis focusing on structural settings of both regimes and key opponents strategies (protests, boycotts, uniting, coalition-building, innovative candidates, major new actors) employed by the opposition in Hungary since 2010 and Serbia since 2012, followed with discussion on findings and conclusions, but also potential disruptive cases that emerged since 2024.

2 THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

The third wave of democratization, particularly in the former socialist states, has also been accompanied by new forms of autocratization. This has occurred through the emergence of transitional regime models that combine democratic procedures and regularly hold elections, thereby satisfying both internal and external demands for democracy. However, in practice, these regimes exhibit various forms of authoritarian practices and sometimes deliberately implement a range of manipulative strategies, both in the electoral arena and in everyday governance. The diversity of these practices has led to terminological variety within political science, with states that fall within this area between liberal democracy and autocracy being referred to as semi-democracies (Case 1993), pseudo-democracies (Diamond, Linz and Lipset 1995), competitive authoritarianisms (Levitsky and Way 2002), semi-authoritarianisms (Ottaway 2003), illiberal democracies (Zakaria 2003), electoral authoritarianisms (Schedler 2006), and most commonly, hybrid regimes (Levitsky and Way 2010). Some of these regimes emerged during the protracted process of democratizing the single party authoritarian systems, while others represent a newer trend – the backsliding of countries that had achieved certain standards of democratic governance (Lührmann and Lindberg 2019).

The survival logic of hybrid regimes revolves around regular quasi-democratic elections, where power is maintained not through military or one-party repressive structures, but through seemingly competitive elections that confer democratic legitimacy on the political regime. This operates on two levels: internally, offering citizens at least a pretence of choice and even a safety valve for political and societal grievances, while providing an image of democratic governance; while externally, presenting the regime as an acceptable partner and member of the international community that adheres to some democratic values. This factor, reinforced by the Serbian and Hungarian regimes' integration into a Western-based order, also contributes to efforts to prevent their transformation into one-party autocracies characterized by overt repression. After all, it is unlikely that Hungary would have retained its position as an EU member, or that Serbia would have been accepted as an EU candidate vividly cooperating with Western democracies, if these regimes had abruptly abolished elections. As a result, hybrid regimes can be fragile and less stable than both genuine democracies and genuine autocracies (see Knutsen and Nygard 2015).

However, the strategies of ruling parties during elections reveal why these democracies are merely a facade, with their political and legal systems reshaped into a sham democracy. Whereas in developed democracies elections serve for power allocation and the exercise of accountability (Bursać and Vučićević 2021); in hybrid regimes, they function as a means of legitimizing the regime. Schedler (2002a) therefore argues that ruling parties will strive to keep competition

limited to the electoral arena, where they retain control over the process, and thus the outcome remains relatively predictable. As a result, the ruling party extensively uses its position and unequal access to institutions (especially the judiciary and independent bodies), public resources, and media, while simultaneously attempting to uphold a minimal standard of democracy that would keep opposition parties in the contest, securing the multiparty competition and providing legitimacy to the race (i.e. Schedler 2013). Hence, openly autocratic and violent methods are rarely employed – as there is simply no need for that.

Within these constraints, the opposition in both countries has attempted various strategies; either in the electoral or in the broader non-institutional arena; but the results have largely been absent. While research on the concept of hybrid regimes has expanded over the past decades – including studies on various forms of these regimes (see, for example: Karl 1995; Diamond 2002; Schedler 2006; Levitsky and Way 2010; Schedler 2013) or the characteristics of elections in these systems and their potential democratizing effects (i.e. Howard and Roessler 2006; Lindberg 2009a; Brownlee 2009; Magaloni 2010; Bunce and Wolchik 2011; Birch 2011; Kaya and Bernhard 2013); the literature on the behaviour of stakeholders within these processes is comparatively limited and predominantly focuses on the perspective of the ruling actor. However, a fundamental characteristic of hybrid regimes that sets them apart from traditional autocracies is the existence of legitimate opposition and the regular occurrence of multiparty elections that are only partly free, fair, or competitive.

The analysis of the opposition's room for manoeuvre and possible strategies is rarely addressed independently in available studies. Instead, it is typically examined through the lens of the regime's authoritarian characteristics, which is somewhat understandable. Within these studies, the most frequently cited factors contributing to the opposition's success are unity and widespread protests authoritarian rule. Diamond (2002) identifies four key elements: mobilization efficiency, a unified opposition, political acumen, and a certain degree of heroism from the anti-regime camp. Similarly, Bunce and Wolchik (2011) emphasize the importance of coalition-building capacities within the opposition and the innovative, creative campaigns they develop. In authoritarian or hybrid regimes, they argue, the opposition faces multiple challenges: organizing effectively against the incumbent party and convincing the public that it can defeat authoritarian leaders in elections and subsequently govern while democratizing the country (Bunce and Wolchik 2009). While such tasks may appear straightforward in democratic contexts, they are far from trivial in authoritarian or hybrid systems. According to the electoral model of democratization (see Lindberg 2009b), an opposition victory depends on ensuring fair elections. Achieving this requires collaboration with civil society, effective voter mobilization, and, critically, the strategic use of street protests or mass mobilization to challenge the regime.

The abovementioned authors argue that genuine opposition unity is a prerequisite for a successful strategy, bringing together all opposition members who agree on the non-democratic nature of the regime. Regional cases from the Western Balkans further demonstrate the importance of large-scale protest mobilization, cross-cleavage cooperation countering the ideological big-tent dominance of regime parties, and opposition cohesion as effective strategies for challenging authoritarian incumbents in Montenegro and North Macedonia (Laštro and Bieber 2021). This unity must include real cooperation with civil society and social movements. A key factor is that opposition parties must view these non-party actors not as challengers or competitors, but as social partners

essential to achieving a common goal. But this dynamic unfolds in an environment where the regime can impose rules that disadvantage collaboration or simply co-opt desirable opposition parties to undermine perceived unity. Bieber (2003) earlier highlighted the Serbian case, arguing that the fall of Milošević in the year 2000 was made possible primarily by unity and broad coalition-building among societal actors, while the persistence of selfish strategies and fragmentation within the opposition in the years before significantly contributed to the regime's prolonged endurance. Furthermore, the presence of political courage, innovation, and creativity is difficult to define as a universal characteristic, as it can vary significantly depending on the political and broader societal context of each country. For example, courage (or heroism, as Diamond terms it) involves taking risks, openly confronting power, and facing the consequences of doing so in order to reveal the authoritarian nature of the system.

In general, participating in such a context requires far greater effort from the opposition, as the political struggle in a distorted and unequal political environment transcends the classical political contest. In other words, to achieve meaningful results, the opposition must go beyond the standard political actions typical for liberal democracies. This framework, based on several previous studies, allows for a comparative analysis of the approaches of the oppositions in two countries, enabling us to propose our hypotheses:

H1: Despite the somewhat different institutional and contextual settings in Serbia and Hungary (type of electoral system, EU membership, external support, ideological roots etc.), the opposition in these types of regimes faces similar manipulations and obstacles.

H2: The shared structural constraints of hybrid regimes condition opposition agency in both Serbia and Hungary, resulting in largely similar strategic choices and outcomes, particularly regarding the adoption (or avoidance) of regime-challenging strategies and their overall effectiveness.

Our analysis will include a comparative case study of electoral cycles in both countries from 2014 onward, focusing on the period from the first parliamentary elections after the establishment of the regime (and the first in which the ruling party has not changed in the electoral arena), covering a decade-long period in Hungary and Serbia. The elections to be considered will include presidential, parliamentary, provincial, and significant local elections in Serbia, as well as parliamentary, European and significant local elections in Hungary. By significant, we define local elections in which voting occurred in capital cities or simultaneously in more than a half of local administrative units. If elections truly serve as an arena for securing legitimacy of a hybrid regime, then the level of government being elected is irrelevant – according to Schedler (2002b), in electoral autocracies, all elections matter as they can either sustain or undermine the autocrat's power and image, both in terms of internal and external legitimacy.

Our methodological approach is primarily analytical and comparative, relying on a structured case study design. As an analytical tool for mapping the opposition strategies and assessing their success, we will design a simple matrix of opposition strategies that encompasses all relevant elections in two countries over a ten-year period. The analytical categories summarized in the matrix will not be treated as isolated tactics, but as a structured set of responses to regime-imposed constraints. In the comparative analysis that will follow, electoral cycles will be assessed through the presence, absence, or partial adoption of these strategies, allowing us to identify patterns of consistency across cases. Rather

than evaluating individual elections in isolation, the matrix enables a longitudinal reading of opposition behaviour within these regimes. The classification of opposition strategies relies on analysis of primary and secondary sources, including election reports and contemporary media coverage, to identify whether, and to what extent, specific strategic dimensions were present across electoral cycles.

3 COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CHALLENGES IMPOSED BY HYBRID REGIMES AND CORRESPONDING OPPOSITION STRATEGIES

Since the opposition is fighting on two fronts, also attempting to shift competition from the electoral arena to the one that questions the overall rules, while the ruling party seeks to keep the political conflict within the formal institutions, frequent concessions are implemented to give opposition hope for the possibility of electoral regime change. In developed democracies, there is a certainty regarding electoral procedures and an uncertainty regarding electoral outcomes, whereas in more authoritarian regimes, the reverse holds true: electoral rules are deliberately designed and manipulated according to the current needs, ultimately maximizing the certainty of the outcomes, that is, the maintenance of the regime in power (Martínez and Coma 2017). The Hungarian example since 2010 demonstrates that the rules of the electoral system have been subject to continuous changes for both local and parliamentary elections. The ruling party consistently utilizes its legislative majority to reshape these rules prior to each election (Tanács-Mandák and Horváth 2025), thereby hindering the opposition's ability to effectively perform the strategic tasks. A similar case can be observed in Serbia, where the ruling parties abruptly lowered the electoral threshold ahead of the 2020 elections to undermine the opposition's boycott and further fragment the opposition landscape.

Opposition parties face multiple challenges in such an environment. Some of the key obstacles inhibiting the opposition that can be identified in both countries and fit the theoretical models of hybrid regime are:

1. Unequal resources between ruling and opposition parties in terms of finances, media, and institutional access;
2. The dual nature of elections, where ruling parties seek legitimacy while the opposition is compelled to compete in elections it deems illegitimate, creating a dilemma whether to participate in an unequal contest and legitimize it – or to abstain from the race and forfeit the resources associated with parliamentary seats (but even when they are represented in parliaments, pressure on the opposition is exerted through legislative procedures and disciplinary measures, as noted by Ilonszki and Dudzińska (2021));
3. Electoral manipulation (rather than blatant ballot stuffing; see Schedler 2002a) through continuous fine-tuning of rules in both countries, including regulations on candidacy, campaign financing, electoral formulas, the timing of elections, and the diaspora vote (in Hungary), as well as opportunistic early election calls, support for various smaller parties to fragment the opposition vote, manipulations of voter register, manipulative definitions of ethnic minority parties, and the nationalization of elections through simultaneous voting for different levels of elections on the same day (in Serbia);
4. Hybrid systems also determine subnational levels of politics (Ross 2014), as seen in both Hungary and Serbia, where local politics is also manipulated, since it can present a nest of survival and entrenchment for the opposition –

- a lesson drawn from Serbia's local opposition islands in the 1990s, which became a springboard for regime change and democratization in 2000;
5. Unrestricted use of media-dominant regime leader during elections, which nationalizes all levels of voting turning them effectively into referendums on the most popular politician who also holds incumbent executive top position – in this context, both Vučić and Orbán serve as proxies for voter information at all levels of elections. But also outside the electoral cycles, both regimes are prone to manufacturing or amplifying crises in order to induce a rally-around-the-flag effect, whereby citizens, in times of instability, seek security from an omnipresent regime that claims to provide it, as described by Sata and Zerkowska-Balas (2025). Beyond criticism, the opposition is usually unable to effectively counter this approach;
 6. A lack of international support for the opposition. Although international actors sometimes verbally condemn regime actions, especially regarding Orbán who is easily brought into conflict with them due to a more comfortable geopolitical position, they are generally unable to assist the opposition in the way seen for example in Serbia under the 1990s Milošević regime: through massive financial, human, know-how, and media support. In the current Serbian situation, there is also a lack of interest from the external actors, as the regime maintains a predictable and mutually useful relationship with them in the context of stabilitocracy (see Bieber 2018).

Overcoming the dominant party in such regimes filled by obstacles, as we have seen, requires, among other things, mobilization, unity, heroism, coalition-building, the creativity and innovative nature of opposition campaigns, or alternatively challenging the very legitimacy of elections (Diamond 2002; Schedler 2002b; Bunce and Wolchik 2011; Laštro and Bieber 2021). In the strategies employed by opposition parties in the two countries over the past decade, we observe examples of each of these behaviours, which led us to identify six analytical categories corresponding to them. Based on these categories, we will examine which strategies opposition parties utilized during electoral cycles. It is important to emphasize that this analysis primarily focuses on the actions of major liberal, pro-democratic, and pro-European opposition parties and movements, even though hybrid regimes in both countries also face relevant opposition from the right-wing spectrum, particularly among populist or nationalist right-wing parties. But as Bunce and Wolchik (2011) suggested, liberal and pro-democratic opposition parties in hybrid regimes primarily emphasize the role of elections as a process of democratization, thus directing their efforts against the regime and its operations. In contrast, the populist right generally has fewer objections to the regime type itself and is more concerned with other government policies, such as socioeconomic, cultural, ethnic, or foreign policy grievances. The six categories we observe are:

1. Major protests, which correspond to pre-electoral voter mobilization;
2. Electoral boycotts, representing a challenge to the legitimacy of the process and shifting the political struggle to the extra-institutional arena, which the regime aims to avoid;
3. Unity, referring to the unification of pro-democratic forces for a joint list and a joint campaign;
4. Coalition-building, which involves forming pre-electoral alliances with opposition parties from the opposite end of the spectrum, primarily with right-wing parties and movements, but also with wider societal actors;
5. New candidates, perceived as new electoral list holders, PM candidates, or presidential candidates, especially when the opposition has managed to mobilize a previously uninvolved but popular public figure as their frontrunner, representing both heroism and innovation or creativity;

6. Major new actors at the elections, which also signifies heroism and creativity, recognizable in the emergence of a new opposition movement or political party (most commonly from the civil society) nested in the pro-democracy camp, that also achieves a notable result in elections and maintains relevance afterwards.

A review of the six categories applied by the opposition in different relevant electoral contests since 2014 (eight in Hungary and eight in Serbia) follows in the matrix below. Using the matrix as an analytical guide, we assess how opposition actors combined (or failed to combine) protest mobilization and extra-institutional contestation with unity, coalition-building, and electoral innovation across successive electoral cycles.

TABLE 1. OPPOSITION STRATEGIES IN SERBIA AND HUNGARY (2014–2024)

Country/ year	Type	Major protests	Boycott	Unity	Coalition- building	New candidates	New actors
SRB 2014	Parliamentary	x	x	x	x	x	x
SRB 2016	Parliamentary, provincial, local	Partial (only after)	x	x	x	x	Yes
SRB 2017	Presidential	Partial (only after)	x	Yes	x	Yes	x
SRB 2018	Belgrade local	x	x	x	x	x	Yes
SRB 2020	Parliamentary, provincial, local	Yes	Yes	x	x	x	x
SRB 2022	Presidential, parliamentary and local	Yes	x	Yes	x	Yes	Yes
SRB 2023	Parliamentary, provincial, local	Yes	x	Yes	x	x	x
SRB 2024	Local	Yes	Partial	Partial	x	Yes	Yes
HUN 2014	Parliamentary	x	x	Partial	x	Yes	x
HUN 2014	European	x	x	x	x	Yes	x
HUN 2014	Local	x	x	x	x	Yes	x
HUN 2018	Parliamentary	Yes	x	x	x	Yes	Yes
HUN 2019	European	x	x	x	x	Yes	Yes
HUN 2019	Local	Yes	x	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
HUN 2022	Parliamentary	Yes	x	Yes	Yes	Yes	x
HUN 2024	European, local	Yes	x	Partial	Partial	Yes	Yes

The matrix captures variation in opposition strategies across selected electoral cycles by indicating the presence, absence, or partial adoption of identified strategic dimensions, where “partial” denotes implementation constrained to only a limited number of subjects. Moreover, the table highlights whether strategies converged around unity and coordination or remained fragmented across opposition actors. These variations allow us to identify patterns of strategic inconsistency that could explain opposition performance over time. Several important trends can be observed from it. The 2014 electoral cycle in Serbia was disastrous for the opposition, which entered parliament with only two lists that together gained just over 12% of the vote. As reflected in the matrix, the opposition failed to adopt almost all available strategic options in those elections. A similar pattern of behaviour, with comparable outcomes, was observed in 2016, when performance improved only marginally: two additional lists (which can be considered new actors) barely crossed the threshold, yet none of the opposition parties secured more than 6.21% of the vote individually, while regime parties once again obtained a supra-majority (see Republička izborna komisija 2025).

The opposition rarely wins, as we have already established before the electoral arena in a hybrid regime is controlled and outcomes are predictable. However, there was one electoral victory within the comparative sample: in the 2019 Hungarian local elections, opposition parties managed to win in Budapest and about a dozen other major cities. The matrix reveals that the opposition employed all strategies within the electoral arena at that time: the election year

began with large protests; there was unity among pro-democratic forces; and a pre-election alliance was formed at the national level with the far-right Jobbik, which held high ratings then; an innovative method of candidate selection through primaries was implemented (see Kazai and Mécs 2019). Additionally, the opposition benefited from a favourable electoral system in the local elections, with direct voting for mayors, which is not the case in Serbia. In this context, the primaries proved to be a wise strategy for kick-starting the prolonged campaign and mobilizing voters beforehand (Mikola and Santos 2025). Ilonszki and Dudzińska (2021) view these elections as an example of a learning curve in cooperative strategies under autocratic conditions that ultimately produced results.

As reflected in the matrix, unity and coalition-building only converged in Hungary in 2019 and 2022, albeit with varying outcomes. In that sense, it is important to explain why ruling Fidesz lost Budapest and other cities in 2019, a sort of an exception confirming the rule. This defeat did not significantly threaten the stability of the regime, nor did it ultimately provide the expected momentum for the opposition, given that the ruling party result in the subsequent 2022 elections marked the largest victory for any party in Hungarian parliamentary vote since the fall of socialism (OSCE 2022). This may also indicate that opposition in such environments struggle to adapt in a timely manner to rapidly changing conditions. On the other hand, the local elections in Serbia in 2023 and 2024 clearly demonstrate that the regime in this country is unwilling to yield even a single town to the opposition, even if this means manipulating their way into power after the elections by using institutional leverage to craft local majorities, as occurred in the cities of Niš and Čačak (see N1 2024a; N1 2024b). Part of the answer to this question lies in the fact that Orbán did not consciously wish to lose the local elections in 2019, but the opposition learned how to compete with Fidesz, at least at the local level, where they employed all the winning strategies as per matrix (Table 1). However, it turned out that the same approach was not sufficient at the national level: the thematic framework of the 2022 campaign was unsuitable for the key issue (the Ukrainian crisis), leading to a lack of mobilization (Reuters 2022). Moreover, the mixed electoral system contained an inherent obstacle: namely, the institutional framework of single-round elections in single-member districts, which required candidates to run in at least 71 districts (a change made before the elections in a manipulative move typical of hybrid regimes), practically imposed unification as a rational choice for all the opposition parties. Nevertheless, building a national coalition between liberals and the left on one side, and the far-right on the other, is no easy task. Although they ran together in the elections, voters punished this broad coalition, awarding them a quarter fewer votes than they had received individually in the previous elections. Namely, in the 2018 parliamentary election, various opposition lists managed to win more than 2.7 million votes combined in the party-list component of Hungary's mixed-member electoral system. The far-right Jobbik party secured 19.06% of the vote, followed by the Hungarian Socialist Party–Dialogue coalition (11.91%), Politics Can Be Different (Hun. LMP, 7.06%), the Democratic Coalition (5.38%), Momentum Movement (3.06%), and Together (Hun. Együtt, 0.66%) – collectively receiving over 47% of the popular vote and translating to 64 seats. However, in 2022, a coalition of these six parties, led by a relatively innovative and successful local leader, Péter Márki-Zay, chosen through primaries mainly for his independent status and potential appeal to conservative voters, garnered only 1.95 million votes (34.44% in the party-list component, 57 seats, see Nemzeti Választási Iroda 2022). Although most of the strategies from 2019 were replicated (apart from the introduction of a new political actor), the opposition's failure highlights that adaptation to the broader

political context is just as important as the institutional conditions of electoral competition, which partially calls their innovativeness into question.

Through a different set of mechanisms – but with similar effects – the Serbian electoral system generates extreme fragmentation. The proportional representation in a single nationwide district and a low threshold of 3% encourages even small parties to participate in elections, as it is relatively easy to gain parliamentary status, resulting in dozens of minor opposition actors on the verge of entering parliament. In contrast, fragmentation in Hungary is not as extreme (due to the single-member district component of the mixed system) and primarily appears to be ideological. However, as we have seen, in such an ideologized competition, cooperation between the two ends of the spectrum can prove difficult. Conversely, due to institutional incentives, such collaboration has not occurred in Serbia during any of the electoral cycles analysed (although it has occurred sometimes during protest activities). Achieving unity is thus challenging, and coalition-building in both countries is even more difficult, as notably visible in the matrix. This was evident in the case of the boycott of the local elections in Serbia in 2024: after the pro-democratic opposition parties engaged together in December 2023 and achieved the best parliamentary result of 24.32% in a Serbian hybrid regime to date (despite heavy violations of electoral rules by the ruling parties, see OSCE 2023) the internal dilemma of whether to remain in the race or question its legitimacy ultimately divided the opposition prior to the local vote and hindered potential tight races in several of the largest cities in the country, where the ruling SNS could have been challenged (NIN 2024).

Both recent boycotts (2020, 2024) of the elections in Serbia were unsuccessful: they did not undermine either the internal or external legitimacy of the regime, partly because external support does not depend on the democratic development in the country itself but rather on the regime's cooperation regarding the foreign policy agenda, in line with the previously explained dynamics of stabilitocracy. Despite this, the regime made efforts both times to facilitate the participation of opposition parties through various concessions (lowering the electoral threshold, introducing even more relaxed rules for ethnic minority parties, adopting concessions regarding the voter register, see OSCE 2020; OSCE 2024), which indicates that there was indeed concern for the legitimacy of the boycotted elections. On the other hand, in Hungary the strategy of boycotting the elections has not been attempted, but street protests and mobilizations have been very frequent.

Often, the opposition's attempts are also not well timed. For example, as matrix demonstrates in Serbia, pro-democratic protests frequently erupt only after elections, as a form of disagreement with the results and the conducting of electoral process, when the outcome is already seemingly irreversible (see BBC 2023). This indicates that the opposition is typically reactive and does not plan, but also that a boycott-or-not dilemma is omnipresent. On the other hand, the large protest movements in Serbia in 2022 and 2023 seemingly facilitated unity and thereby contributed to solid results in the subsequent elections.

It appears that the opposition in both countries lacks a long-term strategy. The Serbian case in general indicates repeated switching between matrix dimensions rather than cumulative strategy-building, while in Hungary, as some authors note (Ilonszki and Dudzińska 2021) and as our analysis confirms, the opposition exhibits a pattern of slow adaptation to the changing political context. Throughout, we can observe significant inconsistency, and in the case of Serbia, even chaotic approach: once again, a prime example of this are the events

between the 2023 and 2024 elections (see Radio Slobodna Evropa 2024), when the entire opposition insisted on electoral irregularities and questioning the system legitimacy, leading to protests and even a hunger strike by several opposition representatives, while completely neglecting the upcoming local elections in 2024 in over 80 cities and municipalities, including the capital, Belgrade – which some of them intended to participate in. In such a context, even the opposition which seems to have previously learned how to build coalitions among themselves fractured, with some opting for a boycott without any hope of undermining the legitimacy of the contest, while others are participating in the elections, without any expectation of victory. This overall represents the worst-case scenario for both camps.

Ultimately, the reason for this situation can also be found in the opposition's relationship with the idea of liberal democracy, which focuses on representative institutions instead of challenging them. In this sense, the restoration of liberal democracy (so often highlighted by the opposition parties) is not a near goal for most voters, as the broader electorate associates these values with the failures of the previous administrations, which hybrid regimes consciously exploit through the media. After all, both regimes were established on the wave of immense dissatisfaction with previous governments, which used to symbolize liberal democracy (Enyedi 2020). Hence Aleksandar Vučić in Serbia often refers to opposition parties as a corrupted elite that led the relatively unsuccessful Serbian transition and whose legitimacy has been damaged by mismanagement of the economy during the global financial crisis and moreover Kosovo's proclamation of independence in 2008 (Bursać and Vučićević 2021). In other words, prevention of democratic decline and restoration of liberal democracy is not relevant to the dominant groups in the society, and their experience of liberal democracy is of an elite-driven political system with neither deep-rooted social traditions nor a significant economic track record that would strengthen its legitimacy. Conversely, Gessler (2025) argues that within authoritarian environments, democratic actors frequently use democracy rhetorically, but as they do not set the political agenda, they end up politicizing their own disempowerment. Apart from institutional constraints imposed by the regime, numerous disadvantages within the electoral arena, and unfavourable international conditions, this may represent an additional conceptual factor explaining why old pro-democratic opposition forces appear to be failing in these two countries.

4 BREAKING THE SPELL: THE EMERGENCE OF NEW ACTORS SINCE 2024

Until 2024, both the Serbian and Hungarian oppositions largely conformed to the strategic inconsistency identified in this study, without seriously challenging entrenched incumbents. Developments since 2024, however, suggest the emergence of qualitatively new opposition configurations that partially transcend this pattern.

In Hungary, the rise of the Tisza party represents a notable departure from earlier dynamics. Triggered by the highly publicized takeover of former Fidesz functionary Péter Magyar, who resigned from government-related positions and rapidly gained nationwide visibility (see Kovarek 2025), Tisza combined several dimensions of our analytical matrix in a manner not previously observed. The party paired political novelty with large-scale protest mobilization and cross-cutting voter appeal, while adopting an organizational logic distinct from

established opposition parties. Its strategy emphasized inclusiveness and internal democracy through wide consultations, grassroots support-building, and the use of primaries for candidate selection (see Hungarian Observer 2025). Meanwhile, it explicitly declines cooperation with existing opposition parties, refusing any alliance with the old opposition (Krizsán 2025).

A broadly comparable dynamic emerged in Serbia, albeit outside the formal party system. Following the collapse of the canopy at the newly renovated Novi Sad railway station in November 2024, which resulted in 16 fatalities, a student-led protest movement gradually evolved into a significant political actor. Rather than articulating conventional liberal-democratic demands, the movement's diffuse and decentralized organizational form challenged established modes of political competition (Zaharijević 2025). It simultaneously exposed the limits of regime-sanctioned pluralism, prompting the authorities to abandon the facade of democracy and resort to open repression. The student movement fulfilled several key conditions of our matrix: it constituted the largest protest mobilization in Serbia to date, attracted broad societal participation, and represented a genuinely new political force. While moving toward institutionalization, it also explicitly rejected cooperation with existing opposition parties, marking a clear break from earlier opposition configurations (Vreme 2025).

Viewed through the lens of our analytical matrix (Table 2), both cases display strikingly similar traits. Each actor emerged with mass protests, articulated an ambition to challenge the regime electorally, and engaged in coalition-building across diverse societal groups (citizens, activists, local organizations), while simultaneously refusing formal cooperation with established opposition. In doing so, both cases call into question the long-standing assumption that opposition unity is a necessary precondition for success against authoritarian incumbents. Moreover, both introduced innovative democratic practices in candidate selection, through formal primaries in Hungary and decentralized parliamentary-list formation via approximately 90 informal student assemblies (plenums) across Serbian faculties (see Mašina 2025). Taken together, both actors seem to compensate full opposition unity through mass mobilization, political novelty, and coalition-building across societal cleavages.

TABLE 2. OPPOSITION STRATEGIES OF NEW ACTORS IN SERBIA AND HUNGARY (2024–2025)

Country	Actor	Major protests	Boycott	Unity	Coalition-building	New candidates	New actors
HUN	Tisza Party	Yes	x	x	Partial	Yes	Yes
SRB	Student movement	Yes	x	x	Partial	Yes	Yes

Although it is not yet possible to assess the full extent to which these actors challenge incumbent regimes, given the absence of parliamentary or presidential elections capable of producing a change in executive power, several electoral contests held during their emergence provide early indicators of their potential. The 2024 European Parliament elections marked a breakthrough for Tisza; merely weeks after Péter Magyar joined the party. It emerged as the second strongest list with 29.6% of the vote. Local elections held on the same day further demonstrated its mobilization potential, as Tisza secured 27.34% in Budapest, despite organizational constraints that limited its participation outside the capital (Kovarek 2025). In Serbia, student-affiliated lists contested local elections in five smaller municipalities during 2025. While these contests did not result in opposition victories, they consistently produced significant declines in vote shares for the SNS, which had easily secured supra-majorities in these localities

before (Nova 2025). Given the structural advantages in terms of widespread clientelism, budget, and media access enjoyed by the ruling party under conditions of hybrid rule (particularly in smaller municipalities) such electoral erosion signifies national electoral potential. Public opinion data further reinforce these trends. In Hungary, polling ahead of the April 2026 parliamentary elections suggests that Tisza represents the most credible opposition challenge in over a decade and could topple Orbán (HVG 2026). In Serbia, although election timing remains uncertain, surveys similarly indicate growing disruptive potential from the student movement (CRTA 2025).

5 CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this study is to provide a comparative insight into the behaviour of the opposition in hybrid regimes, an understudied issue within the generally rich literature on democratic decline and autocratization. This paper's main contribution is synthetic: it systemizes opposition strategies in hybrid regimes to show how structural constraints channel opposition behaviour toward inconsistency and ultimately, electoral failure. We examined the behaviour of opposition in Serbia and Hungary in such unfavourable context through the operationalization of six categories of possible strategies across different election levels from 2014 to 2024, during which the ruling parties in both countries consistently prevailed. Our analysis largely confirms both hypotheses. The findings show that Serbia and Hungary present opposition actors with comparable structural and manipulative constraints (H1), which in turn shape similar strategic behaviours and outcomes across the examined electoral cycles (H2).

We found no differences in the obstacles presented by the regimes (H1), despite the disparities between Vučić's and Orbán's rule in terms of electoral models, ideological foundations, and their respective international positions, meaning that this type of regime produces similar challenges to the opposition. The regime's pressure, in the form of manipulations, as well as the broader conceptual trap of a non-openly oppressive, electoral-bound authoritarian rule, creates a dilemma of participation that is consistent in both regimes. But since the very nature of a modern hybrid regime is not openly oppressive, there is always an option (and an incentive) for opposition parties to run in the elections, which are held in a controlled environment and with similar outcomes, causing opposition to frequently change strategies and approaches. That way, opposition seems more reactive and less strategically adaptable to both institutional and contextual changes of environment. This lack of long-term strategic approach is most apparent in the unstable coalition politics, frequent protest mobilizations, and in Serbia, particularly in the constant switching between electoral and extra-institutional arenas. These inconsistencies, sometimes applied in a chaotic and unplanned manner, despite some limited success (Hungary 2019, and to some extent, Serbia 2023) are perceived as confusing to voters and ultimately hinder their critical mobilization. This further confirms our second hypothesis (H2).

There are certain limitations to our explanation. Despite the transparent analytic structure of the matrix and its grounding in the relevant sources and theoretical literature, the assessment offered in this study remains largely based on the authors' informed but inherently subjective evaluations. A more comprehensive second-stage inquiry would benefit from an expanded methodological approach, including systematic expert surveys, interviews with opposition actors, or quantitative indicators of strategic behaviour and voter mobilization. Moreover,

it is uncertain to what extent the findings can be generalized to all hybrid regimes. Although contemporary hybrid regimes share key conceptual features and impose broadly similar constraints, their effectiveness may vary significantly depending on the specific social and political context. Furthermore, other factors not examined here may also account for the limited success of opposition parties, such as characteristics of their voter base, economic conditions, or broader structural determinants of political competition. Final potential limitation is temporal. While our analysis ultimately focuses on electoral outcomes, this perspective overlooks important developments and the emergence of new actors in both countries since 2024, which may have altered the relative importance of traditional opposition forces versus new political actors. The Serbian student movement and the Tisza Party may therefore constitute boundary conditions for our main arguments, while simultaneously underscoring the growing relevance of new actors in certain political contexts.

These new actors are not associated with the traditional opposition's past shortcomings, such as fragmentation and ineffectiveness. Instead, they have demonstrated the courage, heroism, and creative campaigning strategies emphasized in the literature. If successful, their rise would also suggest that the hybrid regime's institutional and political design long served to contain a stagnant opposition, and that only the emergence of new political actors (in new political contexts) could boost a serious challenge to incumbents. This, in turn, could substantially advance our understanding of what constitutes effective opposition strategies (and credible opposition actors) in hybrid regimes and open new avenues for research of the subject, possibly applicable to other countries as well.

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OPOZICIJSKE STRATEGIJE V HIBRIDNIH REŽIMIH: PRIMERJAVA MADŽARSKE IN SRBIJE

Erozija demokratičnega upravljanja je močno prizadela Srednjo in Vzhodno Evropo, pri čemer več držav doživlja dolgotrajen val avtokratizacije. Prispevek preučuje omejitve, ki jih vzpostavljajo režimi na Madžarskem in v Srbiji, ter strategije opozicije znotraj teh okvirov, pri čemer se osredotoča na proteste, bojkote, volilne taktike in oblikovanje koalicij, pa tudi na njihovo spreminjanje skozi volilne cikle od leta 2014 dalje. Na podlagi strukturiranega primerjalnega okvira prispevek uporablja teoretično utemeljeno analitično matriko za oceno, v kolikšni meri opozicijski akterji soočajo ovire, ki jih postavljajo režimi, ter ali ustvarjajo primerljive strateške odzive. Ugotovitve kažejo, da je nedosleden strateški pristop zaznamoval delovanje opozicije v zadnjem desetletju, kar je verjetno prispevalo k njenim šibkim rezultatom. Ti vzorci so opazni v obeh analiziranih državah in se zdijo v veliki meri neodvisni od institucionalne zasnove, mednarodnega položaja ali ideoloških posebnosti, kar nakazuje, da hibridni režimi omejujejo opozicijske akterje na načine, ki vodijo do podobnih izidov.

Ključne besede: hibridni režimi; opozicijske strategije; volitve; Madžarska; Srbija.